

Optimization and Expansion of Energy Supply in the Electricity Sector of the Democratic Republic of Congo

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Executive Summary

This study examines the optimization and expansion of electricity supply in the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) using the OSeMOSYS energy modeling framework, a cost-optimization tool tailored to meet growing energy demand. The primary goal is to model energy supply scenarios capable of addressing the rising electricity demand in the residential sector, driven by population growth, income increases, and improved electricity access rates.

Three energy-mix scenarios are analyzed: the baseline or business-as-usual scenario (BASE), the governmental ambition scenario (GVT), and the renewable energy integration scenario (RNW). The BASE scenario allows unrestricted investments in any available technology. The GVT scenario incorporates BASE while emphasizing the rehabilitation of existing infrastructure. The RNW scenario excludes fossil fuel investments, prioritizing hydropower and solar energy.

Results indicate that GVT is the least costly scenario, followed by BASE. RNW, while more expensive, is the least polluting. However, the GVT scenario excludes rehabilitation costs, and both BASE and GVT rely on diesel and natural gas plants to meet the government's ambitious targets of 62% electricity access and 30% clean cooking access. RNW is the most suitable for DRC's context, leveraging off-grid hydropower and solar solutions for remote rural areas with limited road access, despite its higher upfront costs.

1. Introduction

The Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC) possesses substantial energy potential, featuring abundant hydrological, solar, forestry, and gas resources. Its hydroelectric potential exceeds 100 GW, yet only 2.4% is currently utilized (Makuku, 2019). The country enjoys favorable solar irradiation between 3.5 and 6.8 kWh/m²/day, paving the way for solar energy development. Furthermore, its vast tropical forests cover 67% of the land and provide biomass resources, alongside significant methane reserves estimated at 278 Gm³.

Despite these resources, energy access in the DRC is critically low. Traditional sources dominate energy consumption, with 96.4% derived from fuelwood and charcoal, while electricity accounts for only 3.3% (AFREC, 2024).

The DRC ranks among the lowest globally in electricity access, impacting approximately 21.5% of a population of 116 million (WB, 2024). This study seeks to determine the optimal energy mix to meet the growing electricity demand in the DRC by 2050, focusing on a strategic milestone in 2030. A key question arises:

What energy supply will optimally satisfy the current and future needs of the residential sector in the DRC?

2. Methodology

The Open Source Energy Modelling System (OSeMOSYS) is an advanced optimisation tool for energy system modelling, designed to simulate various energy scenarios based on future demand, technological options, and expansion capacities, while incorporating economic and environmental constraints (Howells et al., 2017). For the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC), the utilisation of OSeMOSYS enables the design of an optimal energy mix capable of addressing increasing electricity demand while ensuring sustainable and resilient energy solutions.

This study begins by collecting foundational data to calibrate the OSeMOSYS model.(from 2022 to 2024). These inputs include existing electricity generation

capacities, production and consumption volumes, export levels, availability factors, capacity factors, technology-specific efficiencies, and energy demand across key sectors (residential, industrial, transportation, commercial, public services, and agriculture). For this case study, the primary focus is electricity demand within the residential sector; however, industrial, commercial, and public service demands are also considered. Data on installed generation capacity, electricity production, and sectoral energy use were sourced from the Autorité de Régulation du Secteur de l'Électricité (ARE). Additional information on renewable energy resources was obtained from the International Energy Agency (IEA), International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA), and African Energy Commission (AFREC), as well as national agencies under the Ministry of Electricity and Water Resources.

2.1 Modelling energy demand

The modelling of residential electricity demand is aligned with policy ambitions: achieving 62% electricity access and 30% access to clean cooking solutions by 2030, with respective annual growth rates of 6% and 5%. Additionally, an annual increase of 5.3% in average per capita income is assumed. Future electricity demand was projected using an econometric energy consumption formula, integrating these growth parameters.

2.2 Reference energy system

The reference energy system (Figure 1) outlines the technological pathways and resource flows to meet the DRC's energy demand. Resources are transformed into electricity through various technologies, which are then used to meet final demand either via the grid or through off-grid solutions. Off-grid technologies include **hydropower (PWRHYDOF)** and **solar power (PWRSOLOFF)**, while grid-connected options encompass both renewable sources (**PWRHYD**, **PWRSOL01**) and non-renewable energy sources.

Figure 1- Reference Energy System

2.3 Scenarios

Figure 2 provides an overview of the three modelled scenarios: **Baseline**, **GVT**, and **RNW**, which outline different strategies to meet the DRC's energy targets by 2030.

1. Baseline Scenario:

- Government targets include increasing electricity access from 21.5% to 62% by 2030 and encouraging 30% of households to adopt clean cooking solutions.
- Economic growth is projected with a 6% annual increase in per capita income.
- Energy investments focus on new capacity in hydro and solar using a model-free investment approach.

2. GVT Scenario:

- Prioritises infrastructure rehabilitation to improve the reliability of the electricity network.
- Optimises hydropower by increasing capacity and availability factors to 60%.
- Encourages diversified investments across energy technologies.

3. RNW Scenario:

- Builds on the GVT scenario, adding a focus on transitioning to 100% renewable energy starting in 2028, eliminating fossil fuel use entirely.

- Energy mix comprises 75% hydropower (65% on-grid, 10% off-grid) and 25% solar photovoltaic (15% on-grid, 10% off-grid).
- Targets full decarbonisation of the electricity system to minimise environmental impacts.

These scenarios collectively address the DRC’s energy ambitions while considering economic, technological, and environmental factors.

Figure 2 - Scenarios modelled

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Installed capacity of the power sector

Figure 3 shows the current installed capacity and the capacity needed to meet the available demand. PWRHYD and PWRHYDOFF refer to grid-connected and off-grid hydropower plants, respectively. The same applies to PWSOL001 and PWSOLOFF, except these are solar power plants. PWRDSL and PWRNGS refer to grid-connected diesel and natural gas power plants, respectively.

As can be seen, additional capacity is needed to meet existing demand in all three scenarios. This is the current capacity limit. A total of 8.6 GW is expected to be installed in 2024 to meet existing demand, compared to the 3.65 GW installed in 2024, of which only 69% was operational.

To meet the government's target by 2030, the required capacity is 12.51 GW for the baseline scenario (a), compared to 11.55 GW and 20.94 GW for the GVT (b) and RNW (c) scenarios, respectively. The RNW scenario is the most demanding in terms of installed capacity, primarily due to the low capacity factor of the installed solar technology. The GVT is the least demanding. The baseline and GVT scenarios are almost identical, but there is one difference in terms of installed capacity by technology: the GVT scenario assumes that existing power plants will be rehabilitated. This improves the capacity factor, meaning there is less capacity in the GVT scenario than in the baseline scenario.

Figure 3 - Total capacity investment (GW)

3.2 Electricity generation

Figure 4 shows the energy generated by the technology. The information provided above regarding these technologies remains valid. The total energy produced in the DRC in 2024 was 49 PJ (ARE, 2024). The model proposes production of 65 PJ to meet demand.

In relation to the government's electrification target for 2030, the baseline scenario (BASELINE) predicts the generation of 106.02 PJ of energy, compared to 105.6 PJ for the GVT and 92.24 PJ for the RNW.

Figure 4 - Electricity Generation by Technology (PJ)

3.3 Annualized Investment

Figures 5 and 6 show the annual investment costs per technology and the total cost of each scenario by 2050, respectively.

In order to meet the government's 2030 target, the required investments are USD 872.41 million for the baseline scenario, USD 712.67 million for the GVT scenario and USD 3.583 billion for the RNW scenario. The GVT scenario is therefore the most cost-effective, followed by the BASELINE scenario. Compared to the RNW scenario, the difference is significant.

Compared to the DRC's annual energy budget of USD 650 million, the cost per scenario is exorbitant and cannot be covered by the government alone. This is where private investors need to step in.

Figure 5 - Annualized Investment Cost by Technology (USD M)

Figure 6- Difference between scenarios |Total cost by Scenario

3.4 Emissions

Figure 7 illustrates the annual carbon dioxide emission rate by technology. The baseline scenario is the most polluting because it invests in PWRNGS and PWRDSL, the cheapest technologies. This is followed by GNT, which has the same investment policy. Meanwhile, the RNW scenario is the least polluting, achieving total decarbonisation by 2040. This is due to the constraint of not investing in polluting technologies.

Compared to the government's 2030 target, the baseline scenario emits 6.93 ktCO₂, the GVT scenario emits 5.29 ktCO₂, and the RNW scenario emits 0.2 ktCO₂, indicating a tendency towards total decarbonisation of the electricity system.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 3 - Annual emission by technology (ktCO2)

4. Conclusion

The Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) has considerable and diverse energy resources, but faces major challenges in terms of access to electricity and clean cooking solutions. This study aimed to use the OSeMOSYS tool to model the energy supply required to increase access to electricity to 62%, as well as access to clean cooking solutions, by 2030.

As part of this process, we modelled energy demand in the residential sector, making various assumptions and projecting this demand until 2050. Additionally, we broadened our analysis to encompass the industrial, commercial, and public services sectors to account for the DRC's overall electricity demand.

To achieve this, three scenarios were simulated to determine the optimal supply capable of meeting current and future demand. The results showed that the existing electrical capacity and equivalent energy were insufficient to meet short- and medium-term needs. Therefore, the model proposed additional supply in each of the three scenarios.

While the least expensive scenario is not the least polluting, the most expensive scenario is a realistic option for the DRC context as it allows for the maximum exploitation of solar and hydroelectric resources, and is less polluting. Despite its high cost, we recommend that the authorities use it as a basis for improving access to electricity in rural areas. It provides solutions for both grid and off-grid installations. Off-grid solar and hydroelectric power plants appear to be the most suitable option for reaching rural areas, particularly in contexts where the electricity grid is not interconnected at a national level.

The MAED, OnSSET and FINPLAN tools will be essential for future projects, enabling disaggregation of demand by sector, identification of electrified and non-electrified areas, and feasibility studies of proposed projects. Data from the MAED and OnSSET tools will be fed into the OSeMOSYS tool, which focuses on demand analysis.

5. References

1. Mark Howells et al., **OSeMOSYS: The Open Source Energy Modeling System. An introduction to its ethos, structure and development.** *Energy Policy*, vol. 39, no. 10, 2011, pp. 5850–5870. ISSN: 0301-4215. DOI: [10.1016/j.enpol.2011.06.033](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2011.06.033). Available at: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0301421511004897>.
2. Mission 300 AFRICA ENERGY SUMMIT, **Compact énergétique de la République Démocratique du Congo, Connectons 300 M de personnes à l'énergie d'ici 2030.** Powering Africa.
3. International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA), **Energy Transition: Technology – Wind Energy.** Available at: <https://www.irena.org/Energy-Transition/Technology/Wind-energy>.
4. **Global Energy Monitor Projects.** Available at: <https://globalenergymonitor.org/projects/>.
5. African Energy Commission (AFREC), **Data & Statistics – Energy Balances.** 2024. Available at: <https://au-afrec.org/data-statistics-energy-balances>.
6. Levesque Makuku, **Inventory of geothermal sources in the DRC and their development plan for the electrification of local areas: Case of the eastern part of the DRC.** *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, vol. 249, no. 1, 2019, p. 012016. DOI: [10.1088/1755-1315/249/1/012016](https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/249/1/012016). Available at: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/249/1/012016>.
7. ANSER (Agence Nationale d'Électrification et des Services Énergétiques en Milieux Rural et Périurbain), **Plans locaux d'électrification des territoires de la République Démocratique du Congo à l'horizon 2030.** Technical report, Kinshasa, Democratic Republic of Congo, 2022. Available at: https://anser.gouv.cd/wpfd_file/plans-locauxdelectrification-des-territoires-de-la-republique-democratique-du-congo-a-lhorizon-2030/.
8. Autorité de Régulation du Secteur de l'Électricité (ARE), **Rapport Annuel 2024.** Technical report, Democratic Republic of Congo, 2023. Available at: https://are.gouv.cd/bfd_download/rapport-annuel-2024/.
9. United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), **Énergie Durable pour Tous à l'Horizon 2030 (SE4ALL): Évaluation rapide et analyse des gaps.** Technical report, Democratic Republic of Congo, 2013. Available at: <https://www.undp.org/sites/g/files/zskgke326/files/migration/cd/UNDP-CD-RAPPORT-ENERGIE-DURBALE-POUR-TOUS-HORIZON-2030.pdf>.
10. Lucy Allington et al., **Selected 'Starter kit' energy system modelling data for selected countries in Africa, East Asia, and South America.** *Data in Brief*, vol. 42, June 2022, p. 108021. ISSN: 2352-3409. DOI: [10.1016/j.dib.2022.108021](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2022.108021). Available at: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S2352340922002323>.
11. Resource Matters and Energy Systems Research Group, **Électrification de la RD Congo: À la recherche des pistes de solution.** Technical report, Democratic Republic of Congo, Resource Matters and Energy Systems Research Group, University of Cape Town, 2020. Available at: https://cdn.prod.website-files.com/61dedc757232df46a2cf11b3/6430fa1a88264bde3c542ca1_RDC_rapport-v6_compressed.pdf.
12. World Bank, **Access to electricity (% of population) – Congo, Dem. Rep.** 2023. Available at:

<https://donnees.banquemondiale.org/indicateur/EG.ELC.ACCS.ZS?end=2023&locations=CD&start=2019&view=map&year=2023>.

13. IRENA, **Country Indicators and SDGs Energy Profile: Democratic Republic of Congo**. 2023. Available at: https://www.irena.org/-/media/Files/IRENA/Agency/Publication/2023/Jun/Tracking_SDG7_energy_progress_2023.pdf.
14. International Energy Agency (IEA), **World Energy Outlook 2024**. CC BY 4.0. Paris, France: International Energy Agency, 2024. Available at: <https://www.iea.org/reports/world-energy-outlook-2024>.